

**METHODOLOGY AND ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS'
INDEPENDENT WORK.**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'limdagi mustaqil ta'lim topshiriqlari uchun qulayliklar keltirib o'tilgan va bu maqola o'qituvchi va talaba uchun juda foydali ekanligi bayon etiladi. Maqolada mustaqil ta'lim uchun mo'ljallangan mavzular shakli tahlil qilinadi va bu boradagi jahon va o'zbek pedagog vakillarimiz olib brogan ilmiy tadqiqotlarni yoritish asosiy maqsad qilib olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Mustaqil ta'lim, ko'nikma, malaka, tadqiqot, nazariya, amaliyot, funktsiya, baholash, hisobot, o'qituvchi, talaba, intellektual, texnika.

Аннотация: В этой статье упоминаются возможности для самостоятельных учебных заданий в высшей школе, и констатируется, что эта статья очень полезна как для преподавателя, так и для студента. В статье анализируются формы тем, предназначенных для самостоятельного обучения, и основная цель - осветить научные исследования, проводимые в этом отношении нашими представителями мира и узбекскими педагогами.

Ключевые слова: Самостоятельное обучение, навыки, компетентность, исследование, теория, практика, функция, оценка, отчет, учитель, ученик, интеллектуал, методика.

Annotation: In this article, facilities for independent study assignments in higher education are mentioned, and it is stated that this article is very useful for the teacher and the student. The article analyzes the form of topics intended for independent education, and the main goal is to highlight the scientific research conducted by our world and Uzbek pedagogues in this regard.

Key words: Independent learning, skills, competence, research, theory, practice, function, evaluation, report, teacher, student, intellectual, technique.

INTRODUCTION

In the training of future specialists and improving the quality of the educational process, independent work occupies a special place, allowing students to participate in creative activities and develop their intellectual abilities.

Student's independent work is defined as a certain list of topics reserved for independent study, provided with educational and methodological literature and recommendations, controlled in the form of tests, exams, colloquia, abstracts, abstracts and lectures.

Currently, there are different approaches to the method of organizing students' independent work. Some researchers consider independent work as the perception and independent understanding by students of the information presented by the teacher. Others reveal the essence of this phenomenon only by external signs. Others define independent work on the basis of independent assimilation and deep understanding of new knowledge, independent work of students, the amount of time to study the questions posed.

It follows that independent work is not only a form, but also a means of learning, since it forms certain skills and abilities of students, while performing a number of functions: developing, information-educational, orientation-motivating, stimulating, educational and research.

The developing function enhances the culture of intellectual work, introduces them to creative activity, and enriches the intellectual abilities of students. Information and instructions include the learning activities of students in the classroom.

Guidance and encouragement give the educational process the character of a professional orientation.

The purpose of the educational function is the formation and development of the professional qualities of the future specialist.

The research function forms a new level of professional and creative thinking.

The following are distinguished as signs of independent work: the presence of a cognitive or practical task, a problematic issue; task execution time; manifestation of mental stress; Consciousness, independence and activity of students in the process of solving problems; management of independent, cognitive and practical activities of the student. Thus, the core of independent work is a cognitive or problem task that determines the entire learning process.

Independent work is of an activity nature, therefore, in its structure, components characteristic of activity can be distinguished: motivational relationships, setting a specific task, choosing methods of implementation, establishing connections, control.

For successful independent work, the following conditions must be met:

- stimulation of the learning task;
- a clear description of cognitive tasks;
- algorithm, method of performing work, student's knowledge of its implementation;
- the teacher clearly defines the form of the report, the amount of work, the deadlines for its delivery;
- definition of types of consulting support (installation, thematic, problem consultation);
- evaluation, reporting, etc. criteria;
- types and forms of control (seminar, test, test, seminar, etc.).

Independent work includes reproductive and creative processes in the student's activity. Depending on this, three levels of independent work are distinguished.

The reproductive level includes reading educational literature, taking notes, listening to lectures, audio and video recordings, memorizing, retelling, memorizing Internet resources, repeating educational material.

Cognitive research includes the preparation of reports, lectures, presentations at seminars and practical classes, the selection of literature on disciplinary problems, writing abstracts, abstracts, tests, preparation for business games, etc.

The creative level - the level of independent work - includes writing scientific articles, abstracts, participation in scientific research, participation in student scientific conferences, competitions, etc.

The combination of independent work at all levels is necessary for the organization and successful implementation of independent work of students.

According to the level of complexity, four types of independent work of students are distinguished.

The first type forms the ability to perform tasks according to the model. The latter helps to reproduce information from memory. The third is aimed at learning to solve non-standard problems. The fourth involves the performance of tasks aimed at creative activity. A prerequisite for successful independent work is a combination of all of the above types and levels of work.

When organizing students' independent work, it is necessary to take into account the different levels of students' preparation and different styles of learning activities. When choosing assignments, the teacher should be guided by the following criteria

- the volume of each task should be such that, knowing the educational material well, the student can answer all the questions of the task.

ANALYSIS AND METHODS OF THE LITERATURE

Independent work is more effective if a couple or 3 people participate in it. Due to mutual control, group work contributes to an increase in the level of motivation, the development of students' cognitive activity, and interest in joint work. It was made by T.P. Petukhova, I.D. Belonovskaya, M.I. Glotova, M.S. Pashkevich 2012 Monitoring showed the most important and interesting forms of independent work, which were noted by students. This is teamwork on projects, solving typical and complex problems (for subjects of the physics and mathematics block), working with library resources and the Internet (for subjects of the humanitarian block). In addition to additional forms of independent work, students are offered educational and cognitive activities: visiting enterprises, excursions,

applying the considered tasks in production, participating in master classes, internships during training at enterprises and organizations. Later, independent forms of work were proposed, focused on the collective creative cooperation of the participants in the educational process: intellectual competitions, scientific seminars-debates, interuniversity projects, collective projects on the Internet.

There are different forms of reporting on the performed independent work.

- evaluation of the oral response at a practical lesson or seminar;
- solving problems in physics and mathematics;
- an independent conclusion on the topic, compiled according to known information and sources selected by students;
- control and implementation and protection of course work;
- a report on the completion of industrial practice;
- module-rating system of knowledge assessment in the form of electronic tests;
- delivery of subject tests, exams;
- defense of the thesis;
- articles and abstracts written for publication in collections of scientific conferences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pedagogical literature describes various forms of CRS activation. The most effective of them are the following

1. Teaching students the methods of independent work: time guidelines for the implementation of the SHS for planning the time budget; transfer of reflective knowledge necessary for introspection and self-assessment.
2. Convincingly demonstrate the need to master the educational material recommended for future educational and professional activities in introductory lectures, guidelines and manuals.
3. Repetition of typical methods of real thinking used in science and technology, problematic presentation of the material.
4. Use working formulas of laws and definitions to establish a clear link between theory and practice.

5. Application of active teaching methods (case analysis, discussions, group and pair work, collective discussion of complex issues, business games).
6. Development and familiarization of students with the structural-logical scheme of science and its elements.
7. Provide students with methodological instructions, including the algorithm for completing tasks.
8. Development of comprehensive teaching aids for independent work, combining theoretical material, instructions for their solution and tasks.
9. Development of teaching aids of an interdisciplinary nature.
10. Individualization of homework, and in group work, its clear distribution among group members.
11. Adding difficulties to simple problems, giving problems with redundant information.
12. After each lecture, control questions during the lecture.
13. Granting the status of "student consultant" to the most advanced and talented students with comprehensive support.
14. Development and implementation of team teaching methods, groups, couples.

The highest form of SIR is the Student Research Project (TDT). The interdependence of educational and research work contributes to the development of skills and abilities of mental activity, such as analysis, synthesis, generalization, abstraction, systematization. Students are engaged in research activities and write articles, monographs, abstracts, learn to work with refer to reference literature, Internet resources . The research function forms a new level of professional and creative thinking.

CONCLUSION

Research activities develop students' creative thinking. Creative activity is an activity that leads to a new result, a new product.

The main criteria of creative activity include: the novelty of the process of creative activity (new method, technique, mode of action); irrational thinking and

intuition; the ability to independently see and formulate the problem; the presence of a clear emotional experience before finding a solution.

There are four stages of any creative solution: the stage of collecting material, collecting knowledge to help solve the problem; stage of maturity, when it works only unconsciously; stage of perception, when the decision appears unexpectedly; phase of control or verification of results.

Pedagogical and psychological literature describes conditions (situational and personal) that stimulate or inhibit creative activity.

It is noted that lack of time, increased anxiety, impatience when trying to find a quick solution, too strong or weak motivation, self-doubt, etc. negatively affect creative activity.

Personal factors that negatively affect the creative process: compromise, low self-esteem or self-doubt, dominance of negative emotions, avoidance of risky behavior, increased anxiety, etc. Personal characteristics that positively affect creativity are: to risk, not the fear of seeming strange, non-conformity, the presence of a rich imagination, a good sense of humor.

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